

A nanochannel / nanoparticle based filtering and sensing platform for direct detection of a cancer biomarker in blood

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Keywords: Nanopores; nanochannels; CA15-3 ; immunosensing; gold nanoparticles.

A rapid nanochannels based immunoassay capable of a previous filtering and posterior detection of proteins in whole blood without any sample preparation is described. This was accomplished using a nanoporous/nanochannel membrane modified with antibodies whose conductivity toward a red-ox indicator is tuned by primary and secondary immunoreactions with proteins and gold nanoparticles. This interesting nanopores blockage by gold nanoparticles is even enhanced by silver deposition that further decreases the diffusion of the signaling indicator through the nanochannel. The efficiency of the nanochannels to act as immunoreaction platforms including the use of nanoparticles is also monitored by microscopic techniques. Successful detection of immunoglobulins including a cancer biomarker was achieved in buffer as well as in the whole blood. This system constitutes an efficient immunoassay capable of detecting up to 52 U/mL of CA15-3. The developed nanochannel-nanoparticle based device can be used for several other proteins and extended also to DNA detection with interest not only for diagnostics but environmental monitoring, food analysis, safety and security applications.

1. Introduction

There is a strong demand for rapid, high-throughput screening of blood species. The availability of rapid and *in-situ* whole blood assays able to detect various analytes would greatly benefit point-of-care applications. Immunoassays, with their high affinity and specificity, are showing to be the most promising alternative for the implementation of such a system.

Enzyme linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) are not a feasible approach for such a direct detection/diagnostic systems since they require sample purification/separation, incubation, and rinsing steps prior to analysis. A traditional immunoassay is rather time-consuming and labor-intensive.^[1] Surface plasmon resonance, microelectromechanical cantilevers, piezoelectric devices, and microparticle and nanoparticle agglutination assays are a few of the promising immunoassays approaches in development; however, none of these systems have to date achieved a viable direct protein detection in whole blood, being only some lateral flow based immunoassays and microfluidic optical^[2] and electrical^[3] biosensors able for this analysis with minimal sample pretreatment.

More sensitive methods that allow for early detection of protein markers could potentially revolutionize physician treatment of various cancers and diseases and increase patient survival rates.^[4] In this paper, we demonstrate a nanopores/nanochannel based system that uses nanoparticle tracers as blockers capable to detect low concentrations of proteins even in whole blood within minutes without any sample preparation. The combination of nanochannel sensing capability with the known advantages of nanoparticles in immunosensing^[5] is expecting to bring new benefits in diagnostics of proteins.

Nanopores in both synthetic or biological membranes are used as resistive-pulse sensors for molecular and macromolecule analytes. The electrostatic transport through different nanoporous electrodes^[6,7] as well as the size exclusion properties of nonporous films^[8] have

been thoroughly studied in the last years. The most reported applications of nanopores/nanochannels for electrochemical analysis are focused on the DNA sensing. Single stranded RNA or DNA molecules can pass through the wild type α -hemolysin pore in an elongated conformation and the transit time and extent of the current reveal information about the length of the nucleic acid and its base composition.^[9-11] On the other hand, the magnitude of the conductance changes communicates additional details such as the presence of mismatches in DNA sequences. Furthermore, when single-stranded oligonucleotides are covalently attached within the large cavity of the pore, sequence-specific duplex formation can be detected. Based on the same fundament, cylindrical and conical nanopores generated in polymeric membranes^[12] have been applied for DNA^[13-18] and proteins^[19-21] electrochemical sensing. Furthermore, the preparation of silica spheres self-assembled into opal films has also been reported as a promising way to build nanostructured sensing surfaces.^[23,24]

Suitable substrates for DNA sensing are also nanoporous alumina filters. Aluminum anodized oxide disks have a high pore density and small pore diameters, that results in a substrate with high surface area that can be easily functionalized. These filters modified with covalently linked DNA have been used to detect target DNA by monitoring the increase in impedance at the electrode upon DNA hybridization, which results from blocking the pores to ionic flow.^[25,26] In a similar way, the blockage of nanopores by an immunological reaction has been approached for proteins detection measuring changes in interferometric responses.^[27]

However, in most of these biosensing devices the experimental set-up is hard to be built and the final electrochemical measurement is tedious and time-consuming, so alternatives are needed in order to achieve a disposable device for real biosensing applications purposes.

AuNPs have been previously reported by our group to be excellent electrochemical and optical (carrier) labels for DNA^[28,29] and protein^[30,31] analysis after adequate sample pretreatment mostly using magnetic particles as immobilization and immunoreaction

platforms. We even used gold nanoparticles for *in-situ* cell detection taking advantages of their electrocatalytic properties upon hydrogen ions reduction.^[32]

In this work we combine now for the first time the capability of current tuning of a nanopores/nanochannels based platform upon immunoblocking through nanoparticles for the detection of proteins taking advantages of an electrotransducer fabricated by screen-printing technology and a simple voltammetric detection mode. In addition, we show that the use of AuNPs tags as blocking agents improve the detection limits of the label-free immunosensor.

The catalytic properties of AuNPs on the silver deposition, applied also for protein detection,^[33] are approached now to an in-nanochannel enhancement of AuNPs, increasing in a very high extent the pores blocking efficiency and consequently the sensitivity of the assays. In addition to the improvement in the sensitivity, the silver enhancement has the advantage, in comparison with the use of higher sized NPs, that the resulting AuNPs covered with a silver shell can perfectly fit the nanochannel diameter. The blocking would be difficult to be achieved with bigger size NPs due to the non-uniformity in the size of the pores. Finally, we also demonstrate for the first time the efficiency of the developed nanochannel/nanoparticle device for future applications in the direct detection of cancer biomarkers in whole blood where the membranes act as both ‘filtering’ and sensing platform avoiding the matrix effects.

2. Results and discussion

Human IgG detection using different sized AuNPs tags: improving the sensitivity of the label-free assay

The sensing principle for the detection of proteins is schematized in Scheme 1. The formation of the immunocomplexes inside the pores produce a partial blockage in the diffusion of the electroactive species through the nanoporous membranes (B) to the electrochemical transducer surface, resulting in a decrease in the voltammetric signal of the $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ oxidation to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ obtained when the specific reaction does not take place (A) ($\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ are listed in the scheme instead of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ in order to simplify the cartoon). The voltammetric behaviour of this re-dox system can be followed by cyclic voltammetry (see the *supporting information*) but, as it is well known, differential pulse voltammetry is more convenient for quantitative uses (better defined peaks and shorter analysis time) so it was chosen for the obtaining of the analytical signal.

The membrane itself without any modification exerts a certain blocking effect in the pore, compared with the bare SPCE (see the *supporting information*). This effect can be observed as a decrease in the voltammetric peak current. These changes increase when the blocking in the pore is increased due to the immunoreaction, allowing the protein detection.

This is consistent with the relation of sizes between the pores of the nanoporous membrane used (200-nm) and the length of both antibody and antigen (human IgG) that is 14.5 nm x 8.5 nm x 4 nm.^[34] SEM images of a top and a cross sectional view of the nanoporous membranes and are also shown in Scheme 1. Furthermore, a confocal microscopy image corresponding to a top and cross sectional views (of 5 μm from the top and from the bottom) of an AAO nanoporous membrane after immobilizing a human IgG antibody labeled with FITC, following the procedure detailed in *experimental section* is shown. The fluorescence observed in the channels demonstrates that the antibodies are immobilized inside them, being available for the immunoreaction during the next steps.

The detection principle has been approached by our group,^[35] demonstrating the ability of AAO nanoporous membranes to act as sensing platforms and the voltammetric detection by the blockage in the diffusion of indicator electroactive species through the pores due to the

immunoreactions, as a an efficient way to detect proteins in a label-free immunosensor. The main parameters affecting the analytical signal of the label-free immunoassay (antibody concentration, antibody adsorption time, immunological reaction time) have been optimized. The immunocomplex formation has also been monitored by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), being in agreement to the DPV experiments (see the *supporting information*).

However, the sensitivity of the label-free immunosensor (detection limit: 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of human IgG for 200-nm pore membranes) was not good enough to guarantee its application in real samples, where the protein levels of clinical interest usually are below the order of the ng/mL ,^[34] so amplification strategies are required. One of these possible strategies consists in the use of AuNPs tags in immunosandwich assays as blockage agents. This blockage effect of the AuNPs tags in the voltammetric signal of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ oxidation to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ is also schematized in Scheme 1 (C). 20-nm AuNPs were initially chosen since their synthesis and bioconjugation is the most extensively studied and reported and it is a reasonable size in comparison with the diameter of the nanochannels (200-nm), taking also into account that even the human IgG by itself - with a size of 14.5 nm x 8.5 nm x 4 nm - also showed a blocking effect in the pores.^[35]

In Figure 1A are shown the differential pulse voltammograms (DPV) obtained in immunoassays performed for 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of human IgG in a label-free assay (a) and in a sandwich assay using 20-nm AuNPs tags (b) and 80-nm AuNP tags (c). A detailed comparison between the label-free assay, a non specific assay and the sandwich assay using 20-nm AuNPs tags is shown at the *supporting information*. As can be observed in Figure 1A, the AuNPs seem to exert a blockage effect in the pore, which is evidenced in both a decrease in the peak current and also a shift in the oxidation potential to less negative potentials, probably due to the combination of two phenomena: first, the blockage in the diffusion of the

electroactive species through the carbon surface and second, the behaviour of both the electrode and the nanochannel platform as an ‘integrated’ conductive platform.

This enhanced blocking allows to detect up to 2 µg/mL of human IgG using the larger AuNPs tags, a 10-times enhancement compared to that obtained with the smaller AuNPs. The observed sequential decrease in the voltammetric signal by increasing the AuNPs size is an additional control assay, demonstrating that this decrease is due to the steric blockage in the pores.

The presence of the AuNPs inside the channels and their correlation with the concentration of human IgG in the sample was also evaluated by ICP-MS analysis (see the *supporting information*). From this analysis, it can be calculated that 8.9×10^8 AuNPs are present in the channels when the sample contains 100 µg/mL of human IgG, and this quantity increases to 2.2×10^9 AuNPs when the concentration of human IgG is 1000 µg/mL. Comparing these results with the electrochemical measurements, it can be estimated that the presence of approximately 8.9×10^8 AuNPs inside the channels produce a decrease in the voltammetric signal of oxidation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ of 0.35 µA which corresponds to a 40 % decrease of the initial blank signal.

Signal amplification by silver enhancement

In order to detect concentrations of proteins lower than 2 µg/mL the catalytic properties of the AuNPs tags on the silver deposition were approached. After the sandwich immunoassay using 80-nm AuNPs, metallic silver was deposited from a silver salt onto the surface of the AuNPs,

increasing in this way the size of the NPs. The conditions followed in order to control the silver deposition on the gold nanoparticles and to avoid unspecific silver crystals formation are detailed in the *experimental section*. The silver enhancement has the advantage, in comparison with the use of higher size NPs, that the resulting AuNPs covered with a silver shell can perfectly fit the nanochannel diameter. The blocking would be difficult to be achieved with bigger size NPs due to the non-uniformity in the size of the pores (see SEM image in Scheme 1).

The electrochemical measurements obtained are shown in Figure 1A (c voltammogram). For the 5 µg/mL of human IgG assayed, the blockage in the pore is much more pronounced than in the case of the NPs tags without silver enhancement. In this case, a linear relationship between the human IgG and the voltammetric peak current is found in the range between 100-1000 ng/mL (Figure 1B), with a correlation coefficient of 0.9997, adjusted to the following equation:

$$\text{peak current } (\mu\text{A}) = -0.0006 [\text{Human IgG (ng/mL)}] + 0.7229 \quad (n = 3)$$

The reproducibility of the method shows an RSD of 9% ([human IgG]: 500 ng/mL; n=3). The estimated limit of detection, calculated as the concentration of human IgG corresponding to three times the standard deviation of the estimate was in this case 50 ng/mL of human IgG, being this value close to those required in bioassays for the detection of protein biomarkers.^[36] Furthermore, the immunosensor performance in terms of sensitivity and reproducibility is comparable with available optical and electrochemical immunoassays.^[37,5] It can also be noticed that in addition to the $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ oxidation peak, an additional peak at less positive potentials (aprox. 0.0 V) is registered, corresponding to the re-oxidation of the Ag^0 to Ag^+ . This peak is not considered for analytical purposes.

Detection of CA15-3 in blood

One of the most important properties that the nanoporous platforms can offer to biosensing is the fact that they can act as filter agents to biomolecules with sizes higher than the pores diameter. For example, using the 200-nm pores membranes, the typical cells contained in a blood sample will not enter inside the pores and will not interfere in the specific immunoreactions (as schematized in the center of Scheme 1), allowing the detection of proteins in blood without matrix effects, being not necessary the typical sample pre-treatments, such as centrifugation and serum separation.

So the previously optimized immunosensor, based on the sandwich assay using AuNPs labels and silver enhancement was applied for the detection of the cancer biomarker CA15-3 spiked in blood samples. CA15-3 is a glycoprotein mainly used to watch patients with breast cancer.^[38] Elevated blood levels are found in less than 10% of patients with early disease and in about 70% of patients with advanced disease. The normal level of CA15-3 is usually less than 30 U/mL, but levels as high as 100 U/mL can sometimes be seen in women who do not have cancer. Levels of this marker can also be higher in other cancers and in some non-cancerous conditions, such as benign breast conditions and hepatitis.^[39] The CA 15-3 test is performed to aid physicians in the monitoring of treatment of women with invasive breast malignancies. It can also be used to diagnose recurrence of the disease following first-line therapy.

First of all, CA15-3 antigen was detected in PBS buffer following the format assay optimized for human IgG, using 80-nm AuNPs tags and silver enhancement. A blockage effect on the analytical signal was observed again, showing a linear relation between the concentration of CA15-3 antigen and the decrease in the analytical signal in the range 60-240 U/mL.

After that, blood samples of a healthy person with spiked solutions of CA15-3 antigen were also tested. In Figure 2A are shown the analytical signals obtained for blood samples containing three different concentrations of added CA15-3 (60, 120 and 240 U/mL). A comparison of the results obtained in PBS buffer and in the blood sample is shown in Figure

2B. As can be seen, there is a background effect in the blockage of the channels due to the blood matrix, probably due to unspecific adsorptions of the proteins contained in the blood inside the pores, giving rise to a decrease in the voltammetric peak current of approximately 0.15 μA . This background effect remains constant in all the concentrations assayed and does not affect to the sensitivity of the assay. Note that the peak corresponding to the re-oxidation of Ag^0 to Ag^+ at around 0.0 V is also observed, but as explained before, it is not considered. The presence of this peak didn't affect the peak at 0.10V due to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ oxidation used as analytical signal.

In the case of the blood samples, a linear relationship between the CA15-3 concentration and the voltammetric peak current is observed in the range between 60-240 U/mL, with a correlation coefficient of 0.998, adjusted to the following equation:

$$\text{peak current } (\mu\text{A}) = -0.0015 [\text{CA15-3 (U/mL)}] + 0.56 \quad (n = 3)$$

The reproducibility measurements show an RSD of 8% ([CA15-3]: 120 U/mL; n=3) and the estimated limit of detection was 52 U/mL of CA15-3, being this value close to that required in diagnostics.

In Figure 3A is shown a SEM image corresponding to a top view of a AAO nanoporous membrane where a 50 μL drop of blood was deposited (left to dry) on the filtering side. It can be observed that the constituents of the blood (probably rests of red blood cells, white blood cells, platelets and crystal salts; all them in the micrometric scale) remain on the surface of the membrane which acts as filter. The rugosity of both sensing membrane and the cells surface allows the penetration of the electroactive species toward the sensing surface. ^[30]

After the washing step performed before the sample incubation (see *experimental section*) the membranes were observed without these rests on their surface, obtaining SEM images similar to those shown in Scheme 1. When a membrane with immobilized anti-CA15-3 antibodies is left to react with a blood sample containing 240 U/mL of added CA15-3, following the optimized experimental procedure and using 80-nm AuNPs tags and silver enhancement, a

cross-sectional view SEM image as the shown in Figure 3B is obtained. It can observed that the presence of AuNPs inside the pores in the case of the specific reaction, gives rise to the formation of white silver crystals with sizes around 150-200 nm that contribute to the blockage in the pore. The inset image shows a single 80-nm AuNP attached inside a channel without silver enhancement. The presence of silver inside the nanochannels, deposited onto AuNP surface, was also evaluated by Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) microanalysis (see the *supporting information*).

When the same protocol is followed for a blood sample without added CA15-3, no silver crystals are observed, obtaining a cross-sectional view SEM image similar to that shown in Scheme 1, demonstrating the specificity of the assay and the minor interferences of the proteins of the blood (albumins, globulins and fibrinogens) as well as the lipids, glucose, etc. The unspecific AuNPs and consequently silver deposition weren't found as well.

3. Conclusions

A novel immunoassay platform based on nanochannels/nanopores blocking with gold nanoparticles is developed and the advantages of the further silver catalytic deposition are presented. It may show promise in meeting the strong demand for a simple, rapid, in situ whole blood immunoassay. This simple nanochannel blockage induced gold nanoparticles and its further enhancement by silver deposition could be extended to other immunoassays systems. This may open the way to robust immunoassays capable of detecting a variety of clinically relevant proteins. Furthermore, the simplicity of the detection technology requires less technical proficiency than conventional ELISAs and reduces the risk of experimentation error. Assay performance proceeded in a quantitative fashion over the range of 100 to 1000 ng/mL for human IgG. In addition the developed nanochannel-nanoparticle assay also displayed a RSD of 9%. The obtained results demonstrate that, in the absence of the protein used as analyte, no blockage of the nanochannels occurred. The well electrochemical

operation of this technology and its control for false positive / negative controls were also verified by using confocal and transmission microscopies. Some complementary studies were also performed: cyclic voltammograms, electrochemical impedance spectroscopic characterizations and ICP-MS and EDX measurements that validate the reported electrochemical methodology. The developed devices worked also for CA15-3 cancer marker detection spiked in a whole blood, demonstrating a dual ‘filtering’ and detection platform character of the nanoporous membrane, comparable with the commercial lateral flow devices that incorporate filtering systems, but having the advantage of the quantitative analysis that can be performed with the low-cost electrochemical analyzers. Only after the analyte addition does the nanochannel blockage occur. Hence, we have demonstrated an efficient immunoassay capable of detecting 50 ng/mL and 52 U/mL quantities of immunoglobulin and CA15-3 respectively in different media using a simple and low-cost detection technology. The use of less-porous membrane may additionally affect the nanochannel performance bringing advantages for even lower protein detection limits. The nanochannel response tuning by pore size control is being considered now for new nanochannel based platforms. Furthermore, the use of other redox indicators such as ferrocene-methanol and $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_3^{[40]}$ instead of the pair $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ can be also previewed in connection to other nanochannels. Finally, the possibility of a multi-working SPCE modified with several nanoporous membranes is also considered, in order to achieve the multidetection of several proteins in a single assay, that is needed for the accurate diagnostic of many diseases. All this work is now under development at our laboratories.

4. Experimental Section

Chemicals and equipment

IgG from human serum (I4506), IgG from goat serum (I5256), anti-human IgG (I1886 whole molecule produced in goat), anti-human IgG-FITC (Sigma F3512 produced in goat), CA15-3

antigen (B5170, from human serum) hydrogen tetrachloroaurate (III) trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9%), trisodium citrate, 3-amino-propyltrimethoxysilane (APS), [N-(3-dimethylamino)propyl]-N-ethylcarbodiimide (EDC), sulfo N-hydroxysuccinimide (sulfo-NHS) and acetone were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain). Monoclonal (mouse) anti-CA15-3 (ab10120, clone M4H2), monoclonal (mouse) anti-CA15-3 (ab10119, clone M3A106) were purchased from abcam plc (UK).

A fresh blood sample of a healthy person, preserved with heparin, was gently brought by the Hospital Sant Joan de Dèu (Barcelona, Spain). CA15-3 antigen was spiked and homogenized in the blood sample.

Unless otherwise stated, all buffer reagents and other inorganic chemicals were supplied by Sigma, Aldrich or Fluka (Spain). All chemicals were used as received and all aqueous solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Gold nanoparticles suspensions (20-nm and 80-nm in diameter) were purchased from BBInternational (UK). TEM images and the Gaussian distribution of sizes of these suspensions are shown in Figure S1 at the *supporting information*).

The conjugation of AuNPs to anti-human IgG antibodies, was performed according to the following procedure^[30]: AuNPs suspension (2 mL) was mixed with 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of the antibody solution (100 μL) and incubated at 25 °C for 20 min. Subsequently, a blocking step with 1 mg/mL BSA (150 μL), incubating at 25 °C for 20 min was undertaken. Finally, a centrifugation at 4°C and 14000 rpm during 20 min. was carried out, and anti-human IgG/AuNPs conjugates were reconstituted in PBS solution. The same procedure was carried out for the obtaining of the conjugates anti-CA15-3/AuNPs.

The silver enhancement was performed by using a LI SilverTM enhancement kit (Nanoprobes Inc. USA).

Anodized aluminum oxide (AAO) nanoporous filter membranes (Whatman anodisc filters, 13 mm in diameter, 60 μm thick, containing 200 nm pores in a $1 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ pore density) were purchased from Fisher-Bioblock (Spain).

Optical characterizations were performed using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM - Jeol JSM-6300, Jeol Ltd, Tokio, Japan) coupled to a Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) Spectrophotometer ISIS 200 (Oxford Instruments, England) and a Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) Jeol JEM-2011 (Jeol Ltd, Japan).

The electrochemical transducers used were homemade screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs), consisting of three electrodes: working electrode, reference electrode and counter electrode in a single strip fabricated with a semi-automatic screen-printing machine DEK248 (DEK International, Switzerland). The reagents used for this process were: Autostat HT5 polyester sheet (McDermid Autotype, UK) and Electrodag 423SS carbon ink, Electrodag 6037SS silver/silver chloride ink and Minico 7000 Blue insulating ink (Acheson Industries, The Netherlands). The fabrication procedure is detailed at the *supporting information*.

A home-made methacrylate electrochemical cell was used for the electrochemical measurements that were performed with an Autolab 20 (Eco-chemie, The Netherlands) connected to a PC (see pictures of the cell set-up in Figure S2 at the *supporting information*).

Porous membranes functionalization and immobilization of antibodies inside the pores

AAO nanoporous membranes, containing pores of 200 nm in diameter were boiled in nanopure water for 1 h. After drying in Argon they were immersed into 5% acetone solution of APS for 1 h. Then they were washed in acetone and baked at 120°C for 30 min. After that a 1mg/mL solution of anti-human IgG in PBS buffer containing 5 mM EDC/sulfo-NHS (30 μL) was placed on the filtering side and left there during 2 hours. The same experimental procedure was followed for the immobilization of the anti-CA15-3 antibodies.

Sandwich immunoreactions using AuNPs labels

After washing in PBS pH 7.4 buffer, a solution of human IgG in PBS pH 7.4 buffer (30 μ L) was placed on the filtering side of the AAO nanoporous membranes and left there during 1 hour. Finally, AAO nanoporous membranes were washed and stored in PBS buffer. Blank assays were performed following the same experimental procedure, but using goat IgG instead of human IgG. The sandwich assay was completed by placing anti-human IgG/AuNPs (30 μ L) on the filtering side of the AAO nanoporous membranes, and left there during 1 hour. The same experimental procedure was followed for the CA15-3 antigen in PBS and also for the antigen dissolved in blood samples. In this case, the final reaction was performed with anti-CA15-3/AuNPs.

Silver enhancement

The recommendations given by the manufacturer (Nanoprobes Inc.) are followed in order to control the silver deposition around the gold nanoparticles. The two components of the LI SilverTM enhancement kit were previously stored at 4 °C and its reactive mixture was prepared at 24 °C just before using (the stability -no self-nucleation- is guaranteed at this temperature during 45 minutes). The AAO nanoporous membranes were thoroughly washed with deionised water in order to avoid the silver precipitation with rests of chloride, phosphate of other anions that can be present in the sample or the buffers. After that, the reactive mixture (30 μ L) was placed on the filtering side of the membranes and left there for 20 minutes at 24 °C and washed again with milli-Q water.

Nanoporous cell set-up and electrochemical detection

AAO nanoporous membranes were fixed onto the SPCE by a physical attachment, consisting in placing the SPCE onto a methacrylate block and putting the membrane with the filtering

side up covering the three electrodes surface. Then, a second methacrylate block containing a hole of the same size of the working area of the SPCE is placed onto the AAO nanoporous membrane, using an insulating ring between them to avoid liquid's leakage. Finally, the system is fixed using screws. In this way, a 300 μL electrolytic cell of is defined, which is filled with a 1mM $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ in 0.1M NaNO_3 solution (100 μL). (see pictures of the cell set-up in Figure S2 at the *supporting information*). A pre-concentration process at -0.55 V during 30 s was carried out in order to have all the Fe ions in the form of Fe (II) and immediately after, differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) was performed by scanning from -0.40 V to +0.30 V (step potential 10 mV, modulation amplitude 50 mV, scan rate 33.5 mV/s, nonstirred solution), resulting in an analytical signal due to oxidation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ in the range -0.05V to +0.10 V, depending on the blockage of the diffusion of the electroactive specie through the electrode surface. All the voltammetric peak currents represented in the figures correspond to the media of three repetitive measurements performed with three different AAO nanoporous membranes and three different SPCEs. The error bars correspond to the RSD calculated from these measurements.

Acknowledgements

MEC (Madrid) for the projects MAT2008-03079/NAN, CSD2006-00012 ‘‘NANOBIOMED’’ (Consolider-Ingenio 2010) and Juan de la Cierva scholarship (A. de la Escosura-Muñiz) is acknowledged.

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Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))
Revised: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))
Published online on ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Scheme 1. (Center) Scheme of the proteins sensing technology using AAO nanoporous membranes. The cells in the sample remain outside the pores and the proteins enter inside and are recognized by specific antibodies. (Right) Sensing principle in the absence (A) and the presence (B) of the specific protein in the sample and in the case of the sandwich assay using AuNPs tags (C). (Left) SEM images of a top view and a cross-sectional view of the AAO nanoporous membranes containing 200-nm pores and confocal microscope images of a top view and cross sectional views of 5 μm in depth from the both sides of the membranes.

Figure 1. (A) DPVs registered for the label-free assay (a) and for sandwich immunoassays performed using 20-nm AuNPs tags (b), 80-nm AuNPs tags (c), and 80-nm AuNP tags and silver enhancement (d). Human IgG concentration: 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Pre-concentration potential: -0.55 V; pre-concentration time: 30 s; step potential: 10 mV; modulation amplitude: 50 mV; scan rate: 33.5 mV/s. (B) Effect of the concentration of human IgG on the voltammetric peak current for the assay performed using 80-nm AuNPs tags and silver enhancement.

Figure 2. (A) DPVs registered for blood samples containing concentrations of added CA15-3 of 60 (a), 120 (b) and 240 (c) U/mL. DPV parameters are the same as those in figure 1A. (B) Comparison of the effect of the concentration of CA15-3 on the voltammetric peak current obtained in PBS buffer (discontinuous line) and in the blood sample (black line).

Figure 3. SEM images of the AAO nanoporous membrane (200-nm pores) corresponding to **(A)** a top view of a membrane where a 50 µL drop of blood was deposited (and left to dry) on the filtering side. **(B)** a cross-sectional view of a membrane with immobilized α -CA15-3 antibodies, left to react with a blood sample containing 240 µL of added CA15-3 and completing the sandwich using 80-nm AuNPs tags and silver enhancement, observing the white silver crystals. The inset image corresponds to a single 80-nm AuNP attached onto the nanochannel wall.

The anodized alumina membranes act as sensing platforms and at the same time as filters for the detection of proteins in blood samples. The cells contained in blood don't penetrate inside the nanochannels. Finally, gold nanoparticle tags are used for the enhancement of the immunoblocking.

Filtering and electrochemical sensing with nanoporous membranes

Alfredo de la Escosura-Muñiz, Arben Merkoçi

A nanochannel / nanoparticle based filtering and sensing platform for direct detection of a cancer biomarker in blood

Supporting information

A nanochannel / nanoparticle based filtering and sensing platform for direct detection of a cancer biomarker in blood **

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Screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) fabrication

The full size of the sensor strip was 29mm x 6.7mm, and the working-electrode diameter was 3mm. The fabrication of the SPCEs was carried out in three steps. First, a graphite layer was printed onto the polyester sheet, using the screen-printing machine with the stencil (where it is the electron pattern). After curing for 15 minutes at 95°C, an Ag/AgCl layer was printed and cured for 15 minutes at 95°C. Finally, the insulating ink was printed and cured at 95°C for 20 minutes. Images of the 45-sensor sheet obtained following the above experimental procedure and details of one of the SPCE are shown in Figure S3.

Human IgG detection using 20-nm AuNP tags. Comparison with the label-free assay

DPVs registered for immunoassays performed for 1 mg/mL of non specific antigen (goat IgG – a-) and for the same concentration of human IgG in a label-free assay (b) and in a sandwich assay using 20-nm AuNPs tags (c) are shown in Figure S5A. The comparison between the voltammetric peak intensities obtained for different concentrations of human IgG in both kinds of assays is shown in Figure S5B. As can be observed, the AuNPs seem to exert a blockage effect in the pore, which is evidenced in both the decrease in the peak current and also a shift in the oxidation potential to less negative potentials ($\Delta E \sim 220$ mV and $\Delta E \sim 150$ mV compared to the blank assay and to the label-free immunosensor, respectively). Using AuNPs tags in the sandwich assay, the minimum concentration of human IgG able to produce a decrease in the voltammetric signal is 10-times lower (50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) than in the label-free immunosensor, thanks to the blockage effect of the AuNPs. A linear relationship between the voltammetric peak current and the concentration of human IgG is found in the range between 50-200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, with a detection limit of 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, calculated as the concentration of human IgG corresponding to three times the standard deviation of the estimate. The reproducibility of the method shows an RSD of 7% ([human IgG]: 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$; n=3).

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements

The changes in the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in 5mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ after each step of the assay were monitored. The results are presented in Figure S6. The curves correspond to the signals obtained for: a bare SPCE (a), a SPCE modified with a bare membrane (b) and SPCEs modified with membranes: with only immobilized antibody (c), after a non specific immunoassay (d) and after the specific immunoassay (e). As it was expected, an increase in the impedance is sequentially observed, obtaining 5.54, 11.39, 22.36, 22.74 and 54 Kohm respectively.

ICP-MS analysis of the gold contained in the nanoporous membranes

Nanoporous membranes, after performing the sandwich assay using 20-nm AuNPs tags described in the *experimental section* at the main text were dissolved in 2 mL of aqua regia overnight. After that, the samples were 1:10 diluted in HCl 2% and analysed in an ICP-MS spectrometer (Agilent, model 7500ce), measuring the quantity of gold contained in the samples. Three nanoporous membranes were analysed, after performing a non-specific assay with 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of goat IgG and after performing specific assays for 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of human IgG, obtaining absence of gold for the non specific assay and quantities of gold of 0.072 and 0.178 μg for the specific assays respectively. Considering the shape of AuNPs as that of a perfect sphere, the volume of a single 20-nm-diameter particles is calculated to be, 2.09×10^{-18} . By taking the density of the AuNP to be that of bulk gold (ρ), 19.3 g cm^{-3} , the atomic mass (M) to be 196.967 g mol^{-1} , and Avogadro's number (N_A) to be 6.022×10^{23} , the approximate numbers of atoms per particle (N) are, 2.47×10^5 , according with the following equation: $N = \frac{\rho D^3 N_A}{6M}$. From these calculations, it can be estimated that the number of AuNPs attached to the channels through the immunological reaction are:

8.9×10^8 and 2.2×10^9 AuNPs for the two specific assays respectively. These results are summarised in Figure S7.